

Enhancing Youth Empowerment Through Inclusion Of Gandhian Vocational Education In National Education Policy 2020

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Abstract Since ancient times, the traditional Indian educational system has placed a strong emphasis on teaching students how to solve problems in the actual world. It was also intended to equip people with life and career skills. During the British era, this educational system was changed to produce "clerks," which led to a number of problems in the nation, including increased unemployment, corruption, intolerance, and population growth. Mahatma Gandhi, the father of our country, provided us with a blueprint for resolving these issues and empowering youth with his Nai-Talim, or Buniyadi Shiksha, education program. Following independence, the Indian government created a number of commissions, committees, and policies aimed at overhauling our educational system. The National Education Policy 2020 is one such step in putting Gandhi's idea of an educational system into practice.

The National Education Policy 2020 aims to integrate vocational education and offer vertical movement, a feature lacking in previous policies. Its goal is to shift societal perceptions of vocational education and foster a favorable outlook on manual labor, craftsmanship, and self-reliance. This research aims to examine Gandhian vocational education principles emphasizing the holistic development of 'Head, Heart and Hand' i.e. intellect, emotions, and skills. It also explores how these principles are incorporated into the National Education Policy 2020, aiming to nurture an individual 'to develop the whole man' and make India a 'Vishwa Guru'.

Keywords Problem-Solving Skills, Vocational Education, Nai-Talim, Harmonious Development, Gandhian Principles, Youth Empowerment.

Introduction India is the youngest and now has become the largest populated country in the world. Youth in a country is the most viable and potential human resource not only in potential structure but also in social structure. Youth are the major agent for social change, economic growth and technological innovation. (Ministry of statistics and programme implementation, 2022)

But we have not been able to utilise this human resource to the fullest. Faulty education practices have contributed to wastage of talents in the country. The father of our nation, Mahatma Gandhi showed us a path to overcome these problems and empower young population through his education plan known as Nai-Talim or Buniyadi Shiksha. He was a strict advocate of empowering young people with practical knowledge of vocational education to set in motion even those who were considered the poorest and the most backward in society. To mobilize youth power into a powerful asset, the Government of India has taken many steps. One such is the National Education Policy 2020. The National Education Policy 2020 seeks to mainstream vocational education along with providing vertical mobility, which was absent in previous policies.

Objective of study

1. To assess the current state of vocational education in India and analyse its role in youth empowerment.
2. To examine the relevance of Gandhi's vocational education system in the present situation and how these principles align with the goals and objectives of the National Education Policy 2020.
3. To investigate the potential challenges in implementing Gandhian vocational education in the context of the National Education Policy and proposed strategies to address these challenges.

Review of Literature

Soni (2024) in his research paper on National Education Policy(2020): Youth Empowerment through NEP explored making our youth self-dependent by the virtue of Skill Development, and becoming Atmanirbhar. Further, he discussed the concept of Holistic Development through Vocational Courses with different types of essential life skills.

Kakati (2024), explored the congruence between NEP 2020 and Gandhian ideas, shedding light in regards to past indigenous knowledge, vocational education, and decentralization. By integrating Gandhian philosophy with contemporary educational reforms, NEP 2020 aspires to cultivate empowered individuals committed to ethical, inclusive, and sustainable nation-building.

Roy & Guha (2024) discussed the evolution of Indian education from Basic Education to NEP 2020, the key principles of Mahatma Gandhi and the relevance of Gandhiji's Basic education in the present world. Further, the alignment with Gandhian emphasis on holistic development, vocational learning, community involvement, reduced academic pressure, flexibility, and education for citizenship reflects the enduring impact of his educational philosophy on shaping the contemporary educational landscape in India.

Gupta (2022), explored the understanding and relevance of Gandhian Basic Education in contemporary times with reference to NEP 2020 and this paper reveals the gaps in vocational education programs to find out the reasons for marginalization. The paper also deliberated upon the provisions related to vocational skills in the new education policy of 2020. The issues related to skill choices, empowerment, community participation, and the global economy have also been explored.

Sharma (2020), explored Vocational Education and NEP 2020 and discussed about the need and problem of vocational education in the present Education system and about the key recommendations for vocational education in NEP 2020.

Methodology This research is a descriptive study. The data was collected from various websites, including those of the Government of India, magazines, journals, other publications, etc. This data was then analysed.

Analysis

Meaning of Vocational Education

Vocational education or Vocational Education and Training (VET), or Career and Technical Education (CTE) or Technical Education refers to education that prepares learners for jobs that are based in manual or practical activities and are totally related to a specific trade, occupation or vocation. Vocational education also refers to that education in which the learner participates directly and develops expertise in a particular group of techniques or technology. (AICTE, 2017)

Current State of Vocational Education In India

The vocational education in India at present is available at three levels.

1. Vocational curriculum at intermediate level in schools
2. Industrial training institutes (ITI)
3. Three-year courses at Polytechnic

The 12th Five-Year Plan (2012–2017) estimated that only a very small percentage of the Indian workforce in the age group of 19–24 (less than 5%) received formal vocational education, whereas in countries such as the USA the number is 52%, in Germany 75%, and South Korea it is as high as 96%. These figures underline the need to reforming our education structure to meet the needs of 21st century. Consequently, we are just producing degree holders not educated or skilled citizens (NEP 2020, point 16.1, p.44).

To meet the objectives stated in NEP 2020, the paradigm of education should be shifted from-Literacy to education and wisdom, theory-based learning to practical skill oriented learning and desiring government job to job creators.

Source- (Ministry of Human Resource Development)

Role of Vocational Education In Youth Empowerment

Youth can be a positive force for development when provided with knowledge and opportunities they need to thrive. In particular, if young people are given relevant education and skills needed to contribute in a productive economy they turn into a high quality workforce and in turn contribute to social harmony and an increased Human Development Index. Presently, since the demand for Vocational Education is very less but it has a large scope so can be a turning point for bringing a revolution in economic development.

Vocational education involves solving real-world problems. Students while tackling these challenges, use different innovative ideas and techniques. Young people also have the power to act and mobilise others. Hence, they can be the torch bearers for reforming society and removing all inequality and injustice from the society.

Vocational education plays an important role in youth empowerment because it transforms the young population into:

- i) Innovators
- ii) Change-makers
- iii) Critical thinkers
- iv) Communicators

Source- (Ministry of statistics and programme implementation, 2022)

Reasons Of Failure Of Vocational Education In Earlier Policies

1. Wrong attitude of society towards vocational education. The reason of this mindset is because of the history of origin of these courses. These courses were generally made for the school dropouts of grade 8th, 10th or 12th. This has contributed to the negative mindset of society at large.
2. Absence of good quality vocational educational institutions and improper functioning of the regulatory bodies.
3. Unsuitable medium of instruction: mostly the students are from the rural background so they are able to understand better in their local language, but the medium of instruction is either Hindi or English in these institutes.
4. Dearth of teachers: lack of teachers proficient in the required skills is the major issue.
5. Lack of horizontal mobility: the students who want to continue their studies are not able to continue as these courses are short term.
6. Lack of practical aspect: due to lack of resources or paucity of funds hands on training is little or not there.

How These Challenges Are Addressed In National Education Policy 2020

1. Integration of vocational skills from grade six in the school curriculum- since learning begins with action and reflection on the actions, so it is important that students from a young age gain practical learning by hands on training. This would also be helpful in overcoming the social stigma related for vocational education.
2. Transmission of language in a local language- from preparatory and foundational level.
3. Integration of vocational education with general education with a focus on social inclusion, gender equality and inclusive education
4. Horizontal and vertical mobility is initiated.
5. Ensuring professional training for preparation of quality vocational teachers- for this Lok-vidya is emphasized. The specialized local artisans and craftspeople would provide training to the teachers.
6. Promoting online and open vocational education- so that education could be provided in the remotest part of the country. This would also increase the Gross Enrolment Ratio(GER)
7. Incubation centres are to be set up at Higher education Institutes in partnership with industries.
8. Curriculum standardization
 - a. alignment with NSQF (National Skill Quality Framework)
 - b. alignment with International Standards
 - c. alignment for recognition of prior learning(RPL)

Gandhiji's Views on Vocational Education

Nai-Talim etymologically means new education. So Nai-Talim was a form of education system advocated by Gandhiji which wanted to bring a radical change in the then existing society. The main goal of this education was to make individuals self-reliant and, in turn, would empower the villages. Education had in it the inherent philosophy of non- violence, equality and oppression free society.

Four principles of Nai-Talim are:

1. Education in mother tongue along with handicrafts.
2. Work should be linked with the useful vocational needs of the locality.
3. Learning should be linked with vocational work.
4. Work should be socially productive and useful for living.

The main pillars of Gandhian Vocational Education are:

1. Equitable quality education- in the sense that education makes the individual self-reliant and empowered for personal development and social development.to bring a just society where no one is oppressed, no difference would exist between rural and urban.
2. Inclusive education to remove all socio economic barriers from the society. Total personality development of mind, body and spirit.
3. Lifelong learning opportunities- learning for life, learning from life and learning throughout life by socially useful and productive work

Relevance Of Gandhian Philosophy In Present Education Policies

Gandhiji had idealist views and advocated naturalistic methods of imparting knowledge. He favoured that education not only moulds the new generation, but reflects a society's fundamental assumptions about itself and the individuals which compose it. The Wardha scheme of Education, popularly known as Basic Education or Nai-Talim occupies a unique place in the field of education in India. It emphasizes the acquisition of certain minimum knowledge and skills that every child is required to possess irrespective of caste, creed, colour and gender so that they could lead independent, meaningful and peaceful life.

With a tremendous advancement in Science and technology after independence, the young generation needs to keep pace with modern science and technology. But today's generation is facing a gap in the market needs and the social values for which Gandhiji fought throughout his life.

Gandhian vocational education promotes a wide range of skills, from traditional crafts to modern trades. India needs to preserve its rich culture, heritage and craft skills for the generations to come. This need can only be addressed by integrating the vocational skills with the academic curriculum of schools and higher education. It also fosters patriotism in the individuals and deep respect in being an Indian. Vocational education can provide rural populations with skills for livelihoods and economic betterment.

Gandhi's approach to vocational education encourages entrepreneurship and small-scale industries. Entrepreneurship is being promoted by various government schemes like Skill India, Make in India, Stand up India etc. for economic growth and job creation.

In a global context, Gandhian vocational education can contribute to sustainability and ethical practices in international trade and industry. Gandhian vocational education encourages sustainable and eco-friendly practices which would help in tackling environmental challenges and climate change. Thus these principles are more pertinent than ever.

Implementing Gandhian Vocational Education Principles In National Education Policy 2020

1. Holistic development of the individual in both academic and non-academic domains.
2. Interdisciplinary approach- Gandhiji believed that education should be imparted while teaching crafts rather than just from books. Children learn better while learning by doing. National Education Policy 2020 also formulates that no hard separation should exist between arts and science, curricular and extra-curricular, vocational and academic streams.
3. Multidisciplinary and holistic approach to ensure unity and integrity of all languages. Gandhi regarded craft at the centre of the curriculum, integrating and correlating the other subjects with the craft.
4. Emphasis on conceptual understanding rather than rote learning-Gandhiji suggested that by adding craft lessons and vocational training in the curriculum would facilitate intelligent use of bodily organs and inculcate dignity of labour in the young minds. NEP 2020 also aims to achieve the same.
5. Multilingualism- Gandhiji had respect for all languages and believed that the child learns better in his mother tongue. National Education Policy has also emphasized on education in mother tongue. J.B. Kripalani pointed out that the real "medium of instruction" in Basic Education is work, not language; the mother tongue is a medium of communication, not of instruction.
6. Life skills –Gandhiji wanted individual to develop art of living by following ideals of Satya and Ahimsa.
7. Respect for diversity and preservation of culture through education
8. Teachers as heart of the learning process

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The basic crafts suggested by Gandhi and the Committee included- spinning and weaving, carpentry, agriculture, fruit and vegetable gardening, leather work etc. Due emphasis should also be given to developing skills in drawing, music, sports etc.

Job roles identified for implementing the scheme of Vocationalisation of Secondary & Higher Secondary Education by Ministry of Education, Government of India

SECTOR	JOB ROLES	
	Classes 1X and X	Classes XI and XII
	1. Green House Operator 2. Nursery worker 3. Solanaceous crop cultivator 4. Assistant Gardener 5. Pack house worker 6. Bee keeper 7. Non timber forest produce collector 8. Floriculturist (Protected)	1. Micro Irrigation Technician 2. Floriculturist (Open) 3. Dairy Farmer 4. Tuber crop Cultivator 5. Gardener 6. Supply chain field assistant 7. Mushroom Grower 8. Medicinal plant grower 9. Forest nursery raiser 10. Florist

Source (ministry of education, 2017)

In this new scheme, education is linked with vocations thus connecting it to life, through life and throughout life.

Impact of youth empowerment by integrating Gandhian vocational principles in National Education Policy 2020 in future

- Poverty elimination – vocational education can help in breaking the viscous cycle of poverty especially in rural areas and bring economic prosperity.
- Collaborative learning- vocational education tries to bring people with similar mindset together. They collaborate and solve a particular problem, learning through its results.
- Self-satisfaction and self-discipline though self-reliance .India’s youth must remember Mahatma Gandhi’s words, which stated: “Your beliefs become your thoughts. Your thoughts become your words. Your words become your actions. Your actions become your habits. Your habits become your values. Your values become your destiny.”
- Increase in Gross Enrolment Ratio
- Social development
- Improvement in quality of education
- Cleanliness and eco-friendly practices will be promoted
- Lead a pure life based on values - Gandhiji emphasized on the maxim “means are more important than the end”. He wanted every individual should focus on the means, not merely the achievement of an end at any cost. A short cut to achieve pleasure and material gain cannot be a good means for achieving good ends.
- Welfare-state- Gandhiji suggested, the youth should take into consideration various dimensions of their conduct such as the social, cultural, and religious, and they should also make sure that they are meaningfully engaged with the welfare of society. The young people are very vibrant and energetic, dynamic and capable of achieving, provided that they remain on the right track. Hence, it is essential for them to use their energies in a positive way to attain long-term happiness in their life and also contribute to the overall well-being of society.

Potential Challenges In Implementing Vocational Education In India

Implementing vocational education in India can be a transformative endeavour, but it also comes with several challenges. Some potential challenges in implementing vocational education in India include:

- Infrastructure and Resource Constraints:** In a developing country like India, lack of necessary infrastructure, equipment, and qualified instructors to offer high-quality vocational programs is a big challenge. Before education, there are several basic needs like food, water and shelter which need to be addressed and resolved.
- Quality Assurance:** Ensuring the quality of vocational education programs and aligning them with industry standards is crucial. Maintaining a consistently high level of quality across different institutions and programs can be challenging.
- Perception and social stigma:** Vocational education has historically been perceived as inferior to academic education in India. Overcoming societal perceptions and stigmas surrounding vocational education is essential to encourage students to choose vocational paths.
- Curriculum Relevance:** Developing and updating vocational curricula to align with the rapidly changing job market and technological advancements is a continuous challenge. Out-dated curricula can lead to graduates who are not adequately prepared for the workforce.

5. **Teacher Training:** Training teachers needs to be aligned with vocational education effectively. Many teachers may need additional training to teach practical skills and industry-specific knowledge.
6. **Industry Engagement:** Establishing strong partnerships with industries to provide real-world experience, internships, and job placements for vocational students can be challenging. Industries may have reservations about participating in vocational education programs.
7. **Standardization and Certification:** Standardizing certification processes and ensuring that vocational qualifications are recognized and respected by employers can be complex, especially with varying standards across different states and regions.
8. **Access and Equity:** Ensuring that vocational education is accessible to all segments of society, including marginalized groups and economically disadvantaged individuals, is a significant challenge. Barriers to access, such as affordability and geographic location, need to be addressed.
9. **Coordination among Stakeholders:** Effective coordination among government bodies, educational institutions, industry partners, and vocational training providers is essential for a successful vocational education ecosystem. Lack of coordination can lead to inefficiencies and duplication of efforts.
10. **Financing:** Adequate funding for vocational education programs, including infrastructure development, teacher training, and curriculum development, is crucial. Ensuring sustainable financing models can be a challenge, particularly in resource-constrained settings.
11. **Changing Mindset:** Convincing students, parents, and society at large that vocational education can lead to meaningful and lucrative careers is a long-term challenge, given the traditional preference for academic education.

Addressing these challenges requires a multi-faceted approach involving collaboration between the government, industry, educational institutions, and civil society. Policymakers and stakeholders must work together to develop strategies that can make vocational education a viable and attractive option for Indian youth, ultimately contributing to skill development and economic growth in the country.

Conclusion Gandhiji considered education as a means to achieve the utilitarian and cultural aim. It is considered an instrument in the service of the comprehensive development of individual personalities and the needs of the nation. In view of the problems present in society, such as unemployment, inequality, unrest among students, moral degradation and violence, Gandhi's concept of education seems to be the need of the present. Gandhi felt that education should not only increase knowledge but also develop culture in the heart and in the hands. According to him, education without the formation of character was not education.

Gandhiji believed, "Education should not end with childhood as adult education plays an equally vital role in the development of an individual". The learning should be lifelong that develops problem solving skills in an individual so that he would navigate successfully with the ups and downs of his life. So the Gandhian philosophy finds its relevance till there is injustice, inequality and poverty in the society.

Gandhian vocational education may require adaptation to suit modern contexts and technologies but its core principles of self-reliance, skill development, ethics, and community engagement continue to offer valuable insights and solutions for addressing contemporary challenges in education, employment, and sustainable development.

The Reforms suggested by father of our nation for an organized and effective education system depend on proper implementation of the National Education Policy 2020 at all levels. For effective and fruitful results, it is important that both the public as well as private institutions pool resources and empower the future generation with skills of self-sustainability and create a strengthened society free from inequality and discrimination based on any ground.

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